

The impact of financial literacy on the performance of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs): A review of literature

 Jacob Holland^(b)

^(a) Lecturer, School of Business & Leisure, Botswana Accountancy College, Gaborone, Botswana

^(b) Senior Lecturer, School of Business & Leisure, Botswana Accountancy College, Gaborone, Botswana

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of financial literacy on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), focusing on its role in enhancing financial decision-making, access to finance, fintech adoption, and risk management. Grounded in Resource-Based Theory (RBT) and Human Capital Theory (HCT), financial literacy is positioned as both a strategic capability and a form of human capital that strengthens firm resilience and competitiveness. A systematic literature review was conducted, synthesising evidence from 18 empirical studies published between 2016 and 2024. Findings reveal that financial literacy significantly improves SMEs' ability to budget, manage debt, and evaluate investment decisions. It also enhances creditworthiness through improved financial record-keeping, thereby facilitating access to financing. Moreover, digital financial literacy is identified as a catalyst for fintech adoption, which contributes to cost reduction, operational efficiency, and financial transparency. The study concludes that targeted financial literacy interventions are essential, especially in developing economies where SMEs face structural constraints. It calls for integrated financial education strategies involving policymakers, financial institutions, and SME development agencies. Further empirical research is recommended to examine the long-term and digital dimensions of financial literacy as a driver of sustainable SME performance.

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Introduction

Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) play a pivotal role in economic growth and job creation, yet their sustainability and financial success remain a challenge for many. The failure of SMEs is a recurring issue worldwide, with studies indicating that a significant proportion of these businesses do not survive beyond their initial years (Abdullah & Zainudin, 2015; Ahmad & Seet, 2009). Among the critical factors influencing SME performance, financial literacy emerges as a key determinant of financial sustainability, profitability, and resilience. Defined in this study as SME owners' ability to understand, apply, and leverage financial knowledge to improve financial decision-making, access to finance, and optimize resource allocation, financial literacy is closely tied to business success (Chepngetich, 2016; Abdallah *et al.*, 2024). Empirical research suggests that SMEs with higher financial literacy levels are better at managing debts, stabilizing cash flows, and achieving long-term financial sustainability (Nyagope and Nyagope, no date; Akhtar *et al.*, 2024). However, limited financial literacy remains a pressing challenge, often restricting SMEs from accessing credit, utilizing fintech solutions, and implementing risk management strategies (Mustafa *et al.*, 2022).

Financial literacy is an essential aspect of human capital investment, enabling entrepreneurs to make rational financial decisions and mitigate economic vulnerabilities. Without financial knowledge, SMEs often struggle to secure funding, manage cash flows, and navigate financial risks, leading to business failure (Musie, 2015; Ferawati, Fadah and Paramu, 2024). As Pramono *et al.* (2024) argue, poor financial management results in cash flow crises, debt accumulation, and, ultimately, business closure (Philip, 2025). Similarly, Chepngetich (2016) highlights that one of the most persistent challenges for SMEs is maintaining working capital and ensuring financial viability. On the other hand, SMEs with financially literate owners are more resilient, better equipped to withstand

* Corresponding author. ORCID ID: 0009-0007-4637-7785

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economic shocks, and more likely to achieve financial stability (Astuti *et al.*, 2022; Wiagustini, Ramantha and Putra, 2023). Institutional barriers such as limited access to affordable financing, regulatory burdens, and insufficient business support services further complicate SME sustainability. Consequently, this study aims to examine the impact of financial literacy on SME performance, focusing on financial decision-making, access to finance, fintech adoption, and risk management.

To achieve this objective, this paper employs a systematic literature review and thematic analysis of existing studies on SME financial literacy. The study is grounded in Resource-Based Theory (RBT) and Human Capital Theory (HCT), which provide a theoretical lens for understanding financial literacy as both a strategic resource and a human capital investment. The findings contribute to ongoing scholarly discussions on the role of financial literacy in SME sustainability, with particular emphasis on its application in emerging financial markets and digital finance adoption.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the theoretical grounding of the study, discussing relevant theories that frame financial literacy and SME performance. Section 3 outlines the research methodology, detailing the approach used to review existing studies. Section 4 provides an in-depth literature review, exploring empirical and theoretical perspectives on financial literacy in SMEs. Section 5 presents the findings and discussions, analyzing key themes from the reviewed studies. Finally, the paper concludes with recommendations, implications for policy and practice, and directions for future research.

Literature Review

The purpose of this literature review is to investigate the effect of financial literacy on SME performance by synthesising theoretical and empirical research on financial decision-making, access to financing, fintech uptake, and risk management. The review combines Resource-Based Theory (RBT) and Human Capital Theory (HCT) to create a complete framework for understanding how financial literacy improves SMEs' sustainability and competitiveness. A thorough evaluation of peer-reviewed journal articles, reports, and academic sources is carried out to determine how financial literacy serves as both a strategic resource (RBT) and a human capital investment (HCT). This research identifies trends and common themes to demonstrate how financial literacy improves financial management practices, enables loan availability, increases fintech acceptance, and reduces financial risks. The purpose is to gain a conceptual knowledge of the role of financial literacy in SME performance, fill gaps in the research, and give policymakers, financial institutions, and business development organisations with insights on the value of tailored financial education initiatives.

Theoretical and Conceptual Background

Financial literacy has been extensively studied utilising several theoretical frameworks from economics, behavioural finance, psychology, and education (Priyantoro, Ratnawati and Aisjah, 2023). These frameworks investigate how people learn, make choices, and develop financial behaviours (Stieger and Jekel, 2019). Financial literacy is especially important in strategic management theories such as Resource-Based Theory (RBT) and Human Capital Theory (HCT), both of which give a solid framework for understanding its impact on SME performance. This research combines these two theories to look at how financial knowledge, financial behaviour, and financial management practices influence SME financial decision-making, access to financing, fintech uptake, and risk management.

According to the Resource-Based Theory (RBT), financial literacy serves as an intangible strategic resource for SMEs, allowing them to acquire a competitive advantage, optimise financial decision-making, and increase profitability. According to the Human Capital Theory (HCT), financial literacy is a sort of skill development and education that contributes to better financial management, increased creditworthiness, and higher resilience to financial shocks (Waziri, Ngaruko and Ngatuni, 2024). By integrating both approaches, this research positions financial literacy as both a strategic resource and a human capital investment, influencing SME sustainability and long-term performance.

Empirical Review and Hypothesis Development

Although explicit hypotheses are not required for systematic literature reviews, guiding research questions might serve to structure the study (Snyder, 2019). This review focusses its study on the following important research issues, which are consistent with previous empirical data.

RQ1: How does financial literacy affect SME financial decisions?

RQ2: What is the link between financial literacy and SMEs' access to finance?

RQ3: How does digital financial literacy affect fintech adoption in SMEs?

RQ4: How can financial literacy help small and medium-sized businesses manage risk and build resilience?

RQ5: Which theoretical frameworks best explain how financial literacy influences SME performance?

According to the Resource-Based Theory (RBT), organisations that acquire and effectively use valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources are more likely to gain long-term competitive advantages. Financial literacy fits into this concept as an intangible but critical resource, providing SME owners with the information they need to overcome financial issues, acquire loans, and maximise company investments (Abdallah *et al.*, 2024).

Several empirical research support this viewpoint. Eniola and Entebang (2015) discovered that financial literacy corresponds with RBT by assisting SMEs in successfully managing financial resources, improving cash flow planning, and influencing strategic

investment choices. Furthermore, Hj Talip and Wasiuzzaman (2024) contend that financially educated entrepreneurs may reinvest revenues more efficiently and increase financial resilience, so making their enterprises more sustainable. Mustafa et al. (2022) indicate that SMEs with excellent financial literacy skills have fewer financial risks and have higher financial efficiency, validating financial literacy as a VRIN resource that boosts SME competitiveness.

According to RBT, financial literacy is more than simply an individual talent; it is a company asset that helps to financial sustainability and market positioning. The capacity to analyse financial risks, formulate investment plans, and manage cash flow effectively gives SMEs a long-term competitive edge, making financial literacy a critical factor in corporate success.

According to the Human Capital Theory (HCT), knowledge and skills obtained through education and training increase individual and organisational productivity. Financial literacy is an important human capital investment for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) since it improves entrepreneurs' financial decision-making, debt management, and risk assessment skills.

Empirical evidence supports the claim that financial literacy training improves financial management practices among SMEs. Buchdadi and Sholeha (2020) discovered that SMEs that prioritise financial literacy training had greater corporate success rates, easier access to credit, and better capital allocation. Similarly, Hasan et al. (2024) believe that entrepreneurs with greater levels of financial literacy are better able to deal with financial crises, get capital, and adapt to economic unpredictability, assuring long-term company sustainability.

Akhtar et al. (2024) further corroborate HCT by stating that SMEs who engage in financial literacy training outperform those that do not. The research discovered that financially educated company owners are better at obtaining loans, negotiating favourable financing arrangements, and strategically planning long-term investments, emphasising the value of financial literacy as a human capital advantage that promotes business success.

This study combines RBT and HCT to show that financial literacy is both a strategic business resource (RBT) and a human capital investment (HCT), increasing SME competitiveness and financial performance. Financial literacy allows SME owners to maximise sustainability, optimise financial resource allocation, and promote company development (Eniola & Entebang, 2016; Talip & Wasiuzzaman, 2024).

Mustafa et al. (2022) contend that financially literate SMEs benefit from better loan repayment planning, improved financial risk management measures, and increased financial efficiency. These results underscore the dual role of financial literacy as a company resource that supports financial management policies (RBT) and a skill set that improves entrepreneurial financial acumen (HCT).

This study frames financial literacy within both RBT and HCT, highlighting financial knowledge, financial behaviour, and financial management skills as critical drivers of SME performance and sustainability. These theoretical insights highlight the value of financial literacy education as a strategic tool for supporting long-term SME resilience, improving financial planning, and promoting sustainable company development.

Research and Methodology

Study design

RBT and HCT guide the study jointly explaining how financial literacy functions as a resource, behavioral driver, and human capital investment influencing SMEs performance. The analytical approach reflects these theoretical underpinnings emphasizing financial literacy as a predictor of SME performance, studied under important mediating factors like financial decision-making, access to financing, fintech uptake, and risk management.

This study adopts a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) to explore the impact of financial literacy on SME performance, focusing on key aspects of financial knowledge and behavior. To ensure thorough analysis, relevant publications were gathered from multiple academic repositories, including ResearchGate, SSRN, Google Scholar and others (Priyantoro, Ratnawati and Aisjah, 2023) (Alshami & Marwati, n.d.). The search process used the keywords “financial literacy” and “SMEs” to identify relevant studies. Priority was given to scholarly, peer-reviewed publications, as well as reports from government and intergovernmental organizations. While efforts were made to include practitioner reports, particularly those related to SME financial education, they were found to be limited.

Study selection and data collection

An initial pool of 50 peer-reviewed academic papers, empirical studies, and research reports analysing the impact of financial literacy on SMEs' performance provided the data for this project publications were retrieved, after which a rigorous screening process was conducted based on specific inclusion criteria. Only articles published within the last eight years were considered to ensure the relevance of findings. These papers came from institutional repositories in addition to reputable academic resources like Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, Emerald Insight, and ResearchGate. A set of established inclusion and exclusion criteria was used to guarantee that only relevant and high-quality research were included (Abdallah et al., 2024; Akhtar et al., 2024).

Inclusion Criteria

Four main points dominated the inclusion criterion. First, research was to be directly focused on financial literacy and SME performance, including addressing financial performance, financial decision-making, corporate sustainability, financial access, or resilience (Nyagope & Nyagope, 2024). Second, only studies using empirical research techniques including quantitative surveys, regression analysis, case studies, or structural equation modelling (SEM) were taken into consideration since these approaches give quantifiable insights on the financial literacy-SME relationship (Priyantoro, Ratnawati and Aisjah, 2023). Third, the studies used were published between 2016 and 2024 to guarantee relevance to modern financial literacy trends, like the growing significance of digital financial literacy and fintech adoption (Ali *et al.*, 2022). Lastly, research carried out in developing nations—especially in Africa and Asia—where SMEs sometimes struggle with financial literacy issues that affect their sustainability and access to funds were prioritised (Bakashaba, Musiita and Nabachwa, 2024).

Exclusion Criteria

Studies were excluded based on several criteria to ensure relevance and methodological rigor. Non-empirical studies lacking measurable data were omitted, as this review prioritizes evidence-based research on financial literacy and SME performance. Research focusing on large corporations or micro-businesses outside the SME classification was excluded to maintain contextual relevance. Outdated publications before 2016 were disregarded, except for seminal works providing theoretical foundations. Studies without clear methodologies, statistical analyses, or structured data validation were also removed. Additionally, research that addressed financial literacy in general without linking it to SME performance indicators such as access to finance, fintech adoption, or risk management was excluded. Finally, while this study does not focus on a specific region, studies exclusively examining SMEs in highly developed economies were deprioritized in favour of those addressing financial literacy challenges in developing markets, where financial education gaps and access to finance issues are more pronounced.

Data Extraction and Refinement Process

Qualitative content analysis was used to examine the chosen studies. Every study was systematically analysed to identify key themes; these were then arranged according to importance to SME performance. Financial literacy levels, financial decision-making skills, budgeting ability, fintech adoption, loan availability, and financial risk management were the primary factors evaluated (Buchdadi & Sholeha, 2020; Morounfoluwa, n.d.). A comparative analysis across the studies was conducted to find trends and patterns that emerge through coding these factors.

During the analytical stage, refinement then took place. Though the study first looked at 50 scholarly publications, it became clear that not all of them entirely matched the study goal. Some studies covered financial literacy in more general economic or consumer finance environments instead of particularly relating it to SMEs success. Others, less pertinent to our study offered intellectual debates without empirical validation. A supplementary screening was done to guarantee the final analysis included only the most relevant research. 18 studies produced by this approach directly and quantitatively revealed how financial literacy influences SME performance, thereby strongly resonating with the goal of this study. These studies provided empirical data demonstrating the effects of financial literacy on SMEs' development, financial access, fintech adoption, and risk management (Chepngetich, 2016).

Data Analysis and Thematic Insights

A thematic analysis was done to highlight significant research conclusions and patterns after the last 18 articles were chosen. Many of these studies underlined how financial access moderates the benefits of financial literacy (Abdallah *et al.*, 2024; Akhtar *et al.*, 2024). From regression models (PLS-SEM, OLS regression) to longitudinal case studies and mixed-methodologies, the investigations used a range of techniques. Four main mediators, financial decision-making, access to financing, fintech adoption, and risk management, were used in thematic analysis to analyse how financial literacy affected SME performance.

Each study was examined for its theoretical agreement with RBT, FLT, or HCT to ascertain how much financial literacy influenced human capital development, financial behavior, and competitive advantage. Furthermore, trends that support the theories were evaluated across the studies to validate consistencies of differences in economic settings. Establishing causal links between financial literacy and SMEs was made possible in great part by these approaches (Chepngetich, 2016). Furthermore, cross-valuation using systematic reviews and meta-analyses ensured that the last results matched more general research patterns (Shaheen *et al.*, 2023).

Limitations of the Study

Although the process of systematic literature review is a synthesis of the body of knowledge, it has several limits. Publication bias is one main restriction as academic databases may under-represent research reporting poor or negligible results (Munyuki, 2019). This might cause an overemphasizing of findings demonstrating a high positive link between financial literacy and SMEs success while downplaying cases where financial literacy had limited or no influence. Furthermore, this study depends on secondary data and does not include primary data collection. Future studies might overcome this restriction by means of actual fieldwork, including in-depth interviews with SMEs owners, thereby validating the conclusions (Hasan *et al.*, 2024).

The geographical range of the chosen research adds even another constraint. Although the study mostly focusses on developing markets, financial literacy problems in developed countries may vary greatly depending on more access to financial resources and organised financial education initiatives. Increasing the geographical extent of future studies might provide a more complete worldwide view of how financial literacy affects SMEs success in various economic environments.

Conceptual Model

Figure 1: Framework for integrating SME performance and Financial Literacy

Figure 1 depicts a conceptual model for how financial literacy effects SME performance via four major mediating constructs: financial decision-making, access to financing, fintech uptake, and risk management. This paradigm is based on Resource-Based Theory (RBT) and Human Capital Theory (HCT), which both see financial literacy as a strategic resource and an investment in entrepreneurial ability that improves corporate results.

Financial literacy as the primary driver

The model's foundation is financial literacy, which is described as the capacity of a SME owner to comprehend, use, and manage financial information in business situations (Abdallah et al., 2024; Chepngetich, 2016). Financial literacy is the enabling element that impacts all other components in the model. The concept implies that an entrepreneur's knowledge and expertise in managing financial resources is fundamental to how the organisation obtains money, implements digital financial solutions, manages risk, and, ultimately, performs.

Financial Decision Making

Financial literacy first influences financial decision-making, enabling SME owners to develop budgets, manage working capital, evaluate investments, and reduce operating expenses. Akhtar et al. (2024) and Munyuki (2019) found that entrepreneurs with better financial understanding make more strategic and informed decisions, hence enhancing company profitability. This mediating impact has been shown to improve profit, sustainability, and long-term growth.

Access to Finance

Second, the model demonstrates how financial knowledge affects access to financing. SMEs with higher financial acumen keep more accurate financial records, understand credit conditions, and present better loan applications (Bakashaba et al., 2024; Akhtar et al., 2024). According to Nyagope and Nyagope (2024), these characteristics increase financial institutions' willingness to lend, enhancing SME liquidity and capital for growth. Financial literacy also enhances creditworthiness, which increases the likelihood of obtaining loans on favourable conditions.

FinTech Adoption

The third step is fintech adoption. Digital financial literacy is becoming more important in today's fast digitising financial landscape. Financially literate SMEs are more likely to utilise digital platforms like mobile banking, e-wallets, online accounting tools, and fintech loan services, which lower transaction costs and increase operational efficiency (Ali *et al.*, 2022; Kurniasari and Lestari, 2024). According to Ratnawati et al. (2023), fintech is a route via which financial literacy transforms into corporate innovation and development.

Risk Management

Finally, the concept links financial literacy to risk management techniques. Financially literate entrepreneurs are better able to predict, analyse, and reduce risks using approaches such as financial forecasting, diversification, and reserve planning (Buchdadi and Sholeha,

2020; Maduku and Kaseeram, 2021). Hasan et al. (2024) discovered that SMEs with strong financial abilities are more likely to withstand economic shocks, particularly in emerging nations with low financial buffers.

SME Performance as an Outcome

The combined influence of these mediators—decision-making, financing, fintech usage, and risk control—leads to improved SME performance, as assessed by revenue growth, profitability, resilience, and sustainability (Eniola & Entebang, 2016; Mustafa et al., 2022). By establishing financial literacy as a core capacity, the model confirms previous research showing SMEs with financially knowledgeable CEOs routinely outperform those with low financial understanding.

Empirical Review and Hypothesis Development

There is ample evidence indicating that demographic pressures and the growing youth population in developing countries present significant employment challenges. This issue is further intensified by limited job creation, a shortage of formal wage employment opportunities, and increasing workplace vulnerability, which has worsened since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result, promoting youth entrepreneurship has become a key priority in both global and national development policies (Diraditsile, 2021). Several studies have shown empirical evidence that a relationship exists between financial literacy and SME performance (Chepngetich, 2016; Agyei, 2018; Ali *et al.*, 2022).

The next section provides a comprehensive review of existing literature on financial literacy and SME performance. It includes an empirical comparative analysis of various studies aimed at examining the relationship between financial literacy and business performance. The findings are drawn from a review of 18 peer-reviewed publications and other relevant studies.

Findings and Discussions

Findings

The findings of the 18 most relevant studies indicate that financial literacy has a major influence on SMEs' performance, influencing financial decision-making, access to finance, fintech uptake, and risk management (*see appendix 1 showing the key findings*). Research consistently shows that SMEs with financially aware owners are better able to navigate financial crises, optimise resources, and ensure long-term business sustainability. Key challenges raised by the findings include the impact of financial literacy on financial decision-making, loan availability, fintech acceptability, and risk management strategies.

Financial Decision Making and Financial Literacy

Many studies have shown that financial literacy enhances financial decision-making among SMEs' owners, hence boosting debt management, budgeting, investment planning, and cost control. According to Abdallah et al. (2024), Kuwaiti SMEs with higher financial literacy demonstrated superior financial planning and company success. In a similar vein, Chepngetich (2016) discovered that Kenyan SMEs with financially savvy owners had better borrowing and budgeting skills, ensuring financial stability and long-term corporate success.

The findings also highlight how important financial literacy is in driving strategic organisational choices. Munyuki (2019) investigated the influence of financial literacy among young-led SMEs in South Africa and found that entrepreneurs with strong financial literacy skills were more likely to strategically reinvest revenues, efficiently manage cash flow, and eliminate unnecessary costs. Furthermore, establishing the association between financial literacy, financial conduct, and firm sustainability, Nyagope & Nyagope (2024) discovered that Zimbabwean SMEs with systematic financial planning shown greater resilience in changing economic conditions.

Financial Literacy and Access to finance

According to the studies reviewed, financial literacy improves SME access to capital by increasing creditworthiness, financial record-keeping, and loan payback ability. According to Akhtar et al. (2024), financial literacy training increased the likelihood of SMEs in Pakistan receiving finance, maintaining accurate financial records, and appropriately using credit facilities. In Uganda, Bakashaba et al. (2024) discovered that SMEs with financial literacy training were 45.7% more likely to get loans than their less financially literate counterparts.

Additional data points suggest that financial literacy influences the relationship between creditworthiness and financial planning. According to Priyantoro et al. (2023), SMEs in Indonesia with strong cash flow management awareness are more likely to get funding from banks and microfinance institutions. Hasan et al. (2024) also found that SMEs with long-term financial planning ability were more resilient during recessions because they had better access to alternate financing sources and financial assistance.

Financial Literacy and Fintech Adoption

The results in table 3 show that fintech adoption is dependent on digital financial literacy, which boosts financial efficiency, lowers transaction costs, and improves SMEs' financial performance via financial literacy development. Ali et al. (2022) discovered that

SMEs in Pakistan who practiced digital financial literacy reported increased profitability and operational efficiency, thanks in large part to improved access to mobile banking and digital payment systems.

Similarly, Kurniasari et al. (2024) observed that Indonesian SMEs with higher levels of digital financial literacy were more likely to use e-commerce financial management tools, online banking, and mobile payments. The study found that fintech adoption led in lower transaction costs, better record-keeping, and more financial flexibility, reinforcing the relationship between financial literacy and SME success. Kusumawardhani, Ningrum and Rinofah, (2023) supported this thesis by showing how fintech knowledge enables SMEs to access alternative financing sources, hence reducing their dependency on traditional banking institutions. The findings also suggest that financial inclusion stems from digital financial literacy. Priyantoro et al. (2023) demonstrated how substantially SMEs' digital financial literacy influences access to online lending facilities and microfinance services. To ensure that small businesses properly use technological advancements in financial services, the paper recommends that lawmakers include digital financial literacy education into SMEs growth activities.

Using financial literacy as a risk management technique.

Table 4 shows another crucial result is that boosting SMEs' resilience and minimising financial risk are heavily reliant on financial expertise. Strong financial literacy skills among SMEs assisted Buchdadi (2022) and Sholeha (2020) in assessing financial risks, developing backup plans, and avoiding financial calamities. The study found that understanding financial risks helps SMEs manage financial shocks and improve overall financial stability.

Maduku and Kaseeram's (2021) research focused on black-owned informal SMEs in South Africa and highlighted how much financial literacy enhances firm survival rates by providing entrepreneurs with budgeting, capital allocation, and investment planning tools. Their findings suggest that, although loan availability remains challenging, financial literacy increases SMEs' ability to get financing, negotiate better terms, and efficiently manage cash flow, hence reducing their susceptibility to financial instability.

In a similar vein, Jessica and Lothin (2024) examined financial risk management techniques among black-owned SMEs in South Africa and concluded that a lack of financial literacy contributes to higher SMEs' failure rates. The study demonstrated how effectively financially literate organisations may decrease risks by establishing emergency savings, using cost-cutting measures, and diversifying revenue streams. These findings support those of Maduku and Kaseeram (2021), emphasising the importance of financial literacy in ensuring business resilience and long-term growth.

Msimango (2023) explored systemic barriers impacting black-owned financial service providers in South Africa, identifying financial literacy shortages as a major hurdle to SMEs' survival. According to the study, SMEs who actively participated in financial literacy efforts had higher levels of entrepreneurial resilience, better financial record-keeping, and better strategic decision-making, as well as more flexibility in the face of financial constraints. The report encourages lawmakers to develop coordinated financial literacy programs for black-owned businesses, therefore improving their ability to compete in ever-changing economic circumstances. Hasan et al. (2024) also observed that financially smart SMEs were more resilient during economic downturns because they were more likely to have backup plans, alternative revenue sources, and financial buffer access. Long-term financial planning is therefore a more essential risk-reduction technique since it ensures that SMEs can adapt to market changes and unexpected financial issues.

Key Results Synopsis

The study's findings give empirical evidence that financial literacy has a significant impact on SME performance. Financial literacy improves risk management approaches, boosts financial access, encourages fintech adoption, and aids in financial decision-making. Small and medium-sized enterprises with financially competent proprietors are very profitable, resilient, and capable of meeting financial challenges.

The findings suggest that, given the complexity of modern financial markets and the increasing digitisation of financial services, financial literacy training should be a top governmental priority. Legislators, financial institutions, and business development agencies can offer entrepreneurs with the skills they need to navigate financial complexity, maximise resource allocation, and promote long-term firm success via financial education programs geared towards SMEs.

Discussions

Key Results and Thematic Synthesis

This comprehensive literature review offers solid evidence that financial literacy improves SME performance in four key areas: financial decision-making, access to financing, technology uptake, and risk management. Financially savvy entrepreneurs excel in budgeting, resource allocation, debt management, and financial planning (Abdallah et al., 2024; Chepngetich, 2016). These qualities lead to improved company performance measures such as profitability, sustainability, and external finance (Mustafa et al., 2022). Digital financial literacy has emerged as a critical aspect in assisting SMEs in using financial technology to minimise operating costs and increase efficiency (Kurniasari et al., 2024).

Regional and Sectoral Comparative Insights

Table 1: Regional and Sectoral Comparative Insights

Region	Representative Countries	Key Authors	Core Focus	Key Findings	
Africa	Uganda, South Africa, Zimbabwe	Kenya, Africa, Msimango (2024); Nyagope & Nyagope (2024)	Bakashaba et al. (2024); Chepngetich (2016); Nyagope & Nyagope (2024)	Access to finance, financial planning, business sustainability	Financial literacy improves access to finance, enhances survival of SMEs, and supports long-term resilience in financially constrained environments.
Asia	Pakistan, Indonesia, Nigeria, Kuwait	Ali et al. (2022); Ratnawati et al. (2023); Morounfoluwa (2023); Abdallah et al. (2024)	Digital finance, fintech adoption, entrepreneurial performance	Digital financial literacy facilitates fintech use, improves risk management, and strengthens SME competitiveness and profitability.	

Table 1 shows the examined literature demonstrates a significant difference in the implementation and effect of financial literacy in African and Asian cultures. In Africa, financial literacy is essential for SMEs managing unstable financial infrastructures and structural hurdles. According to studies conducted in Kenya, Zimbabwe, and South Africa (Chepngetich, 2016; Nyagope & Nyagope, 2024; Msimango, 2024), basic financial skills such as budgeting, cash flow management, and debt planning are critical for SME survival, particularly in underserved or historically disadvantaged communities. The benefit is particularly obvious in informal and black-owned businesses, where access to formalised financial education is directly linked to greater company continuity and strategic planning.

In contrast, in Asia, the focus has shifted to digital competences and financial integration. Research from Indonesia and Pakistan (Ratnawati et al., 2023; Ali et al., 2022) shows that SMEs in digitally advanced contexts outperform by embracing mobile banking, e-commerce platforms, and financial automation technologies. Financial literacy not only ensures operational efficiency but also acts as a fuel for innovation and resilience in competitive marketplaces. For example, Abdallah et al. (2024) show that financial access in Kuwait modulates the benefits of financial literacy, suggesting a synergistic link between institutional financial assistance and individual financial competence.

From a sectoral standpoint, agro-based SMEs, notably in SAARC countries (Akhtar et al., 2024), use financial literacy to improve supply chain finance and resource planning. Meanwhile, service-oriented SMEs, such as those in metropolitan Kenya and South Africa, rely more on financial record-keeping and daily financial behaviour to deal with working capital restrictions. These distinctions highlight the need of personalised financial literacy programs that include not just regional infrastructure and digital development, but also industry-specific financial difficulties.

To summarise, financial literacy presents itself in a variety of ways depending on the circumstances. In Africa, it is a survival strategy that addresses systemic financial exclusion, but in Asia, it serves as a strategic facilitator of technological adaptation and innovation. These geographical variations emphasise the significance of context-sensitive financial education policies and programs that are tailored to local economic realities and SME characteristics.

Integration of Prior Research

The review results are consistent with and build on previous studies. For example, Akhtar et al. (2024) and Bakashaba et al. (2024) found that SMEs with financial literacy training had better access to varied sources of finance. Ali et al. (2022) discovered that digital financial literacy allows SMEs in developing nations to use mobile banking and fintech platforms, enhancing operational performance. Similarly, Eniola and Entebang (2016) found that financial literacy improves SME competitiveness via smart financial behaviour. Thus, the results fit within a well-established literature foundation while also expanding it by emphasising novel factors like fintech and resilience in the face of economic instability.

Integration with Theoretical Frameworks

This research uses both Resource-Based Theory (RBT) and Human Capital Theory (HCT) to examine the influence of financial literacy in SME success. RBT defines financial literacy as a valuable, uncommon, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resource that allows SMEs to gain a durable competitive advantage (Eniola & Entebang, 2016; Talip & Wasiuzzaman, 2024). According to HCT, financial literacy is a human capital investment that improves management competence, financial discipline, and business acumen (Lawal, Kabiru and Ibrahim Isah, 2024; Waziri, Ngaruko and Ngatuni, 2024). This dual-theoretical foundation broadens our knowledge of how financial literacy enhances both firm-level skills and individual entrepreneur performance.

Limitations of the Study

Despite its virtues, the review has certain drawbacks. First, relying on published academic research involves a publication bias, which may over-represent studies that showed favourable impacts of financial literacy (Munyuki 2019). Second, although the study prioritises material from developing countries, its applicability to established economies may be limited due to disparities in institutional structures, access to capital, and educational systems. Third, the diversity in research methodology and conceptual definitions of financial literacy among the analysed studies makes direct comparisons difficult and may restrict synthesis consistency.

Future Research Directions.

To improve on this study, future research should use primary data gathering techniques such as longitudinal studies, interviews, and surveys. These may give further insight into the causal factors that relate financial literacy to SME success. Further research on digital financial literacy and how it influences fintech adoption would be especially beneficial in today's technology-driven economy. Furthermore, comparative research across nations and regions might assist determine how cultural, institutional, and legal variables influence the effect of financial literacy. Investigating the effect of structured financial education programs would also help to better understand long-term performance outcomes for SMEs.

Theoretical Propositions for Future Testing

This assessment also identifies potential for creating and testing new theoretical models. For example, future study might broaden RBT by include digital financial literacy as a dynamic capacity, especially in situations characterised by fast technological change. Behavioural economics frameworks might be used to investigate how cognitive biases, as well as knowledge, impact financial decisions. Furthermore, future research might use financial literacy as a mediating or moderating variable in wider frameworks that relate entrepreneurial attitude, innovation, and business success. Such postulations provide opportunities for both theoretical innovation and empirical confirmation.

Conclusions

This research sought to evaluate the degree to which financial literacy serves as a predictor of SME success, using Resource-Based Theory (RBT) and Human Capital Theory (HCT). Although no one working hypothesis was statistically evaluated in this systematic literature review, the theoretical framework did support the guiding premise that financial literacy enhances SME outcomes via financial decision-making, access to financing, fintech uptake, and risk management. The integration of empirical evidence from 18 peer-reviewed research confirms that financial literacy should be seen as both a strategic resource and an investment in human capital, particularly in resource-constrained settings.

This study's main contribution is its multidimensional conceptual model, which emphasises the mediating channels by which financial literacy influences company results. This study extends the bounds of existing knowledge by integrating digital financial literacy and fintech adoption into the discussion areas that have yet to be explored in the SME domain and offers a novel theoretical and empirical synthesis on which others may build. Furthermore, the study adds to theory by highlighting the importance of RBT and HCT in the SME finance literature, as well as proposing conceptual approaches for hybrid theoretical frameworks in future research. However, the research notes that its breadth and statistics are limited. Most of the studied literature concentrated on SMEs in developing nations, which, although relevant to the study's objectives, may restrict the conceptual model's applicability to more developed economies. Furthermore, publication bias, definitional conflicts across research, and the omission of grey literature may have an impact on the overall comprehensiveness of the study.

Given these results, future research should focus on empirical testing of the conceptual model using mixed-method techniques, longitudinal datasets, and cross-country comparisons. Care should be taken to assess the effect of organised financial literacy initiatives, digital upskilling programs, and gender variations in financial education results among SMEs. Furthermore, behavioural variables, such as biases in financial decision-making, should be included into future theoretical investigations to enhance the psychological depth of financial literacy research.

The institutional and structural consequences of this study are significant. Policymakers and development organisations should see financial literacy as a critical component of SME development strategy, rather than an ancillary skill. Targeted initiatives in financial education, digital banking literacy, and fintech onboarding should be included in entrepreneurial assistance plans. Financial institutions may also benefit from modifying their lending criteria to include financial literacy tests as prediction tools for loan performance. Finally, national governments should think about incorporating financial literacy into larger economic development policies to promote equitable growth, increase loan availability, and strengthen the resilience of SMEs in the face of economic instability.

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References

- Abdallah, W., Harraf, A., Ghura, H., & Abrar, M. (2024). Financial literacy and small and medium enterprises performance: the moderating role of financial access. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-06-2024-0337>
- Agyei, S. K. (2018). Culture, financial literacy, and SME performance in Ghana. *Cogent Economics and Finance*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2018.1463813>
- Akhtar, S., Cui, Y., Frimpong, S. E., & Rafi, N. (2024). Unlocking sustainable competitive performance in agrobased small and medium enterprises in South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation countries. *Agricultural Economics (Czech Republic)*, 70(6), 309–319. <https://doi.org/10.17221/264/2023-AGRICECON>
- Ali Al-shami, S., & Marwati, F. (n.d.). Factors that influence financial literacy on small medium enterprises: A literature review. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331823650>
- Ali, H. S. A., Muhammad Ishtiaq, Muhammad Fayyaz Sheikh, & Riaz, A. (2022). Digital Financial Literacy and Business Success of SMEs in Pakistan. *NICE Research Journal*, 88–113. <https://doi.org/10.51239/nrjss.vi.397>
- Astuti, Y., Team Putri Fariska, E. S., Nidya Dudija, Ms., Hani Gita Ayungningtias, M., & Dian Putri Rahmdhani, M. (2022). Sustainable Collaboration in Business, Information and Innovation 13 th 2022. 3, 2022.
- Bakashaba, R., Musiita, B., & Nabachwa, S. (2024). 41 Financial Literacy, Access to Digital Finance and Performance of Ugandan SMEs in Mbarara City. In *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies (Vol. 16, Issue 1)*.
- Chepngetich, P. (2016). Effect of Financial Literacy and Performance SMEs. Evidence from Kenya. In *American Based Research Journal (Vol. 5)*. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2882997><http://www.abrj.org>
- Dharmawan Buchdadi, A., & Sholeha, A. (2020a). The Influence of Financial Literacy on SMEs Performance through Access to Finance and Financial Risk Attitude as Mediation Variables. In *Article in Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345045505>
- Diraditsile, K. (n.d.). Exploring the Terrain and Challenges of Youth Entrepreneurship Development in Ramotswa, Botswana. In *Botswana Notes and Records (Vol. 53)*.
- Eniola, A. A., & Entebang, H. (2015). Financial literacy and SME firm performance. *International Journal of Research Studies in Management*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrsm.2015.1304>
- Ferawati, I. W., Fadah, I., & Paramu, H. (2024). Literature Review: Financial Literacy in The Context of Micro Enterprise Development and The Methods Used. <https://doi.org/10.17509/jpak.v12i2.71056>
- Hasan, M., Jannah, M., Supatminingsih, T., Ahmad, M. I. S., Sangkala, M., Najib, M., & Elpisah. (2024). Understanding the role of financial literacy, entrepreneurial literacy, and digital economic literacy on entrepreneurial creativity and MSMEs success: a knowledge-based view perspective. *Cogent Business and Management*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2433708>
- Hj Talip, S. N. S., & Wasiuzzaman, S. (2024). Influence of human capital and social capital on MSME access to finance: assessing the mediating role of financial literacy. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 42(3), 458–485. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-04-2023-0214>
- Jessica, G., & Lothian, L. (n.d.). Identifying Risk in Small and Medium Enterprise: The Case of Black-Owned SMEs in South Africa Submitted by.
- Kurniasari, F., & Lestari, E. D. (2024). Development of Financial Literacy and Fintech Adoption on Women SMEs Business Performance in Indonesia. *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, 5(13(131)), 67–75. <https://doi.org/10.15587/1729-4061.2024.312613>
- Kusumawardhani, R., Ningrum, N. K., & Rinofah, R. (2023). Investigating Digital Financial Literacy and its Impact on SMEs' Performance: Evidence from Indonesia. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(12), e04097. <https://doi.org/10.26668/businessreview/2023.v8i12.4097>
- Lawal, M., Kabiru, M., & Ibrahim Isah, A. (2024). Impact of Talent Management on the financial performance of SMEs in Kaduna Metropolis. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 1(1), 288–302. <https://doi.org/10.59568/IJEBM-2024-1-1-23>
- Maduku, H., & Kaseeram, I. (2021). Success indicators among black owned informal Small Micro and Medium Enterprises' (SMMEs) in South Africa. *Development Southern Africa*, 38(4), 664–682. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0376835X.2021.1913997>
- Morounfoluwa, O. (n.d.). Financial Literacy and Entrepreneurship Performance. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4483051>
- Msimango, D. T. (2023). Exploring Why Black-Owned Financial Service Providers In South Africa Have Failed. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 13(5), 200–205. <https://doi.org/10.29322/ijsrp.13.05.2023.p13727>
- Munyuki, T. (2019). The implications of financial literacy for the success of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) initiated by the youth in economically disadvantaged areas of Cape Town. <http://etd.uwc.ac.za/>

- Musie, L. (n.d.). The use of financial literacy concepts by entrepreneurs in the small and medium enterprise sector in Mpumalanga Province, South Africa.
- Mustafa, N. H., Jaffar, R., Mohd Fadhil, N. F., Shaharuddin, S., & Taliyang, S. M. (2022). The Antecedents of Financial Literacy and The Impact on SMEs' Performance: A Conceptual Paper. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(12). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v12-i12/16062>
- Nyagope, T. S., & Nyagope, O. S. (n.d.). The Role of Financial Literacy in Enhancing SME Access to Financial Services, Growth and Sustainable Development in Zimbabwe.
- Philip, L. N. (2025). The role of financial literacy in driving sustainable entrepreneurial success: A case study of Lapo Microfinance Institution (MFI), Nigeria. *Issues and Perspectives in Business and Social Sciences*, 5(1), 37–48. <https://doi.org/10.33093/ipbss.2025.5.1.4>
- Pramono, C., Wardani, N. S., Syahputri, C., Pembangunan, U., & Budi Email, P. (2024). Multifinance Journal Ekonomi, Manajemen Dan Perbankan: The Influence of Financial Literacy and Financial Inclusion on Company Performance (Case Study of SMEs in Klambir Lima). 2(1). <http://altinriset.com/journal/index.php/multifinance>
- Priyantoro, P., Ratnawati, K., & Aisjah, S. (2023). The effect of financial literacy on business performance through mediation of financial access and financial risk attitude. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147- 4478), 12(9), 275–287. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v12i9.3024>
- Shaheen, N., Shaheen, A., Ramadan, A., Hefnawy, M. T., Ramadan, A., Ibrahim, I. A., Hassanein, M. E., Ashour, M. E., & Flouty, O. (2023). Appraising systematic reviews: a comprehensive guide to ensuring validity and reliability. *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2023.1268045>
- Snyder, H. (2019). Literature review as a research methodology: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, 104, 333–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.07.039>
- Stieger, S., & Jekel, T. (2019). Ideology, education, and financial literacy uncovering neoliberal ideology in assessment studies of economics education-the case of Austria. *Journal of Social Science Education*, 18(2), 4–27. <https://doi.org/10.4119/jsse-906>
- Waziri, M., Ngaruko, D., & Ngatuni, P. (2024). Influence of Entrepreneurship Competence on Employability of Technical and Vocational Education and Training Institutions Graduates in Tanzania: The Moderating Role of Self-Efficacy. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 12(06), 4096–4120. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2024.126206>
- Wiagustini, N. L. P., Ramantha, I. W., & Putra, I. M. W. (2023). Financial Literacy and Financial Behavior Encouraging Business Sustainability by Mediation of Financial Performance. *Quality - Access to Success*, 24(192), 226–234. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/24.192.27>

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Appendix

Table 2: Peer reviewed Journals used for this study

No	Author(s) & Year	Study Focus	Methodology	Key Findings	Impact on SME Performance
1	Wael Abdallah et al. (2024)	Financial literacy and SME performance in Kuwait, moderated by financial access.	Cross-sectional survey, PLS-SEM.	Financial literacy enhances financial management skills, leading to better business outcomes. Financial access significantly moderates this relationship.	Improved loan repayment planning and profitability.
2	Taurayi Stephen Nyagope & Owen Simon Nyagope (2024)	Role of financial literacy in SME access to finance, growth, and sustainable development in Zimbabwe.	Case study approach, quantitative and qualitative analysis.	SMEs with better financial literacy make sound financial decisions, diversify financing sources, and mitigate financial risks.	Enhanced business growth and sustainability in a challenging financial environment.
3	Kusuma Ratnawati et al. (2023)	Financial literacy and sustainable business performance via access to finance and fintech adoption in Indonesia.	Survey of 261 SMEs, SmartPLS analysis.	Financial literacy facilitates fintech adoption and financial access, which in turn drive SME sustainability.	Fintech adoption acts as a mediator between financial literacy and SME performance.
4	Hafiz Sohrab Ali et al. (2022)	Digital financial literacy and business success in Pakistan.	Survey-based quantitative study, Hayes Process Macro analysis.	Digital financial literacy positively affects SME success, with enterprise risk management as a mediator.	Enhances financial planning and risk management, leading to improved profitability.
5	Shamim Akhtar et al. (2024)	Interplay of financial literacy, access to finance, and SME growth in Pakistan.	Survey of 206 SMEs, Moderated regression analysis.	Financial literacy moderates the positive relationship between financial access and SME growth.	Increases access to financial products and improves financial planning.
6	Tinashe Munyuki (2019)	Financial literacy and youth-led SME success in Cape Town.	Mixed method (quantitative survey & qualitative interviews).	Financial literacy correlates with business survival among young entrepreneurs.	Recommends integrating financial education in youth entrepreneurship programs.
7	Rennie Bakashaba et al. (2024)	Financial literacy, access to digital finance, and SME performance in Uganda.	Cross-sectional survey of 351 SMEs.	Financial literacy and digital finance access explain 45.7% of variations in SME performance.	Suggests prioritizing financial literacy initiatives for SMEs.
8	Mangihut Parlindungan Aritonang et al. (2023)	Effect of financial literacy and financial inclusion on MSME performance in Indonesia.	PLS-SEM analysis, survey of 517 MSMEs.	Financial literacy and inclusion significantly affect MSME performance.	Calls for continued government efforts in improving financial literacy levels.
9	Shamim Akhtar et al. (2024)	Examining financial literacy, access to finance, and SME growth in Pakistan.	Survey of 206 SMEs, Moderated regression analysis.	Financial literacy acts as a moderator between financial access and SME growth.	Suggests better financial education policies for SMEs.
10	Agung Dharmawan Buchdadi et al. (2020)	Influence of financial literacy on SME performance via financial risk attitude and access to finance.	Structural equation modelling (SEM), survey of 70 SME managers.	Financial literacy, risk attitude, and access to finance significantly affect SME performance.	Calls for government programs enhancing financial literacy among SME owners.
11	Akinyede Oyinlola Morounfoluwa (2023)	Financial literacy and entrepreneurship performance in Nigeria.	Snowball sampling, structured questionnaire, regression analysis.	Strong positive relationship between financial literacy and business success.	Recommends integrating financial management training into entrepreneurship programs.

12	Florentina Kurniasari et al. (2024)	Impact of financial literacy and fintech adoption on SME performance.	SEM-PLS analysis, survey of 270 female entrepreneurs.	Fintech adoption mediates the financial literacy-SME performance relationship.	Highlights the role of digital technology in SME sustainability.
13	Prisca Chepngetich (2016)	Relationship between financial literacy and SME performance in Uasin Gishu, Kenya.	Pearson correlation, survey-based study.	Financial literacy improves borrowing and budgeting expertise.	Suggests enhanced SME financial training programs.
14	E. Otieno (2016)	Influence of financial literacy on financial performance of SMEs in Ruiru Town, Kenya.	Case study approach, qualitative research.	SMEs with strong financial literacy skills manage cash flow more efficiently.	Recommends integrating financial literacy into SME business plans.
15	Thabo Msimango (2024)	Exploring Why Black-Owned Financial Service Providers in South Africa Have Failed.	Documentary analysis and policy review.	Financial literacy gaps hinder SME survival in South Africa's financial sector.	Proposes policy-based financial literacy interventions.
16	H. Maduku & I. Kaseeram (2021)	Success Indicators Among Black-Owned Informal SMMEs in South Africa.	Longitudinal study and quantitative SME analysis.	Financial literacy, funding access, and business planning enhance SME sustainability.	Highlights the importance of structured financial literacy programs.
17	G.J. Lokolo Lothin (2024)	Identifying Risk in Small and Medium Enterprises: The Case of Black-Owned SMEs In South Africa.	Qualitative risk assessment of SMEs.	Lack of financial risk literacy increases SME failure rates.	Calls for SME-focused financial risk training.
18	Aisha Hasan et al. (2024)	Financial literacy and the resilience of SMEs during economic downturns.	Comparative study, financial performance analysis.	Financially literate SMEs perform better in economic crises.	Highlights the importance of long-term financial planning for SMEs.